

CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL COMBINATIONS USED WITH ZOONYMS IN AZERBAIJANI AND FRENCH LANGUAGES

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ANALYSE CONTRASTÉE DES COMBINAISONS PHRASÉOLOGIQUES UTILISÉES AVEC LES ZOONYMES EN LANGUES AZERBAÏDJANAISE ET FRANÇAISE

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Abstract

Phraseological combinations arising from zoological onomastics exist in every language. In the French and Azerbaijani languages, there are many phraseological expressions with zoonym characteristics and they are distinguished by their functionality in the language. The theoretical and practical importance of these expressions, which are the main composition of the onomastic lexicon, has been the object of contrastive research by linguists in many languages. The functional and metaphorical characteristics of expressions used with zoonyms in the phraseological dictionary of French and Azerbaijani languages, and in some cases the homogeneity and heterogeneity of these expressions in languages with two different systems are of interest. Narratives, legends, and stories play a major role in the creation of many phraseological combinations in both Azerbaijani and French languages. People have been inspired by nature since ancient times and created phraseological combinations related to each part of it. These phraseological combinations that have survived to this day are colorful and rich in modern Azerbaijani and French languages. They are distinguished by their lexical-semantic and functional characteristics, carrying the characteristics of emotionality and imagery in the language. Phraseological expressions related to zoonyms are widely used in both Azerbaijani and French languages.

Abstrait

Des combinaisons phraséologiques issues de l'onomastique zoologique existent dans toutes les langues. Dans les langues française et azerbaïdjanaise, il existe de nombreuses expressions phraséologiques présentant des caractéristiques zoonymes et elles se distinguent par leur fonctionnalité dans la langue. L'importance théorique et pratique de ces expressions, qui constituent la composition principale du lexique onomastique, a fait l'objet de recherches contrastées de la part de linguistes dans de nombreuses langues. Les caractéristiques fonctionnelles et métaphoriques des expressions utilisées avec les zoonymes dans le dictionnaire phraséologique des langues française et azerbaïdjanaise, et dans certains cas l'homogénéité et l'hétérogénéité de ces expressions dans des langues à deux systèmes différents, sont intéressantes. Les récits, les légendes et les histoires jouent un rôle majeur dans la création de nombreuses combinaisons phraséologiques en langue azerbaïdjanaise et française. Les gens se sont inspirés de la nature depuis l'Antiquité et ont créé des combinaisons phraséologiques liées à chaque partie de celle-ci. Ces combinaisons phraséologiques qui ont survécu jusqu'à ce jour sont colorées et riches en langues azerbaïdjanaises et françaises modernes. Ils se distinguent par leurs caractéristiques lexicales-sémantiques et fonctionnelles, portant les caractéristiques de l'émotivité et de l'imagerie dans la langue. Les expressions phraséologiques liées aux zoonymes sont largement utilisées en langue azerbaïdjanaise et française.

Keywords: phraseological combinations; phraseology; phraseology; zoonyms: stable word combinations; free word combinations

Mots-clés : combinaisons phraséologiques ; phraséologie; phraséologie; zoonymes : combinaisons de mots stables ; combinaisons de mots gratuites

Phraseology is a Greek word, pharis means "expression" and logos means "science". The term phraseology is a combination of the words meaning and science. The set of indivisible expressions and phrases of all stable word combinations in the language is called phraseology [3, p. 260]. The words in the phraseology are its components. Phraseological units can be two-component, three-component, three-component and more components, etc. can be. One of the main features of these language units is that they are figurative and

emotional. It reflects national values, people's way of life, civilization.

Each language contains words of wisdom, proverbs, proverbs, aphorisms, and phraseological combinations. Phraseology is the main part of lexical composition in French and Azerbaijani languages. When translating in the languages being compared, there is either a complete match or no equivalent is found. In this case, it is necessary to use different translation methods, for example, the kalka method, the explanatory

translation method. If there is no equivalent in the translated language, it is necessary to look for a synonym or choose a stylistically close one. Narratives, legends, stories play a big role in the creation of some phraseological combinations. For example, *başı əhlət daşına dəymək* (hitting the head on the birthstone), *bışmiş toyuğun gülməyi gəlir* (a cooked chicken laughs), və *dəvəsi ölmüş ərəb* (an Arab whose camel is dead) [2, p. 47].

Phraseological units can be homonymous, synonymous, antonymous and polysemic (multiple meaning) according to their meaning. As a source of their creation, we can cite folk language, fiction, and folklore as an example. In linguistics, there are different motives and reasons for the emergence of these language units. For example, religion, superstition (Being in Heaven, Noah's storm), professional art (Give the hat to the hatter, and one more), lifestyle (hanging food), tradition (cutting salt and bread), historical figures (Seeing Nadir on the throne), There are expressions related to folk literature (burn like Karam). Some phrases are used figuratively and symbolically to form phraseological units. We encounter certain difficulties when translating phraseological units in different system languages. Although phraseological units in languages belonging to the same language family undergo phonetic transformation, they have the same meaning, they are common expressions. However, in languages belonging to different language families, these expressions rarely have homogeneous features. There is a connection between the onomastic lexicon of linguistics and phraseology. Phraseological combinations include anthroponyms, ethnonyms, toponyms, hydronyms, cosmonyms, phytonyms, zoonyms.

Zoonyms is a Greek word, *zoon* means animal, *onoma* means name and learns animal names [3, p. 252]. Zoonyms, which make up the most interesting layers of the lexical composition, include lexical semantic groups such as insects, reptiles, birds, fish, amphibians. In linguistics, the branch of onomology that deals with special zoonyms is called "zoonymics" [4, p. 41].

Babayev Javid mentions zooonomastics in his article: "here can be another field of onomastics - zooonomastics which is the naming of places with animals' names. For instance, We ate a delicious lobster at Gazelle (restaurant)" [1, p.45].

Most of the phraseology in the language is made up of phraseological units used with zoonyms. Since ancient times, animals have been a part of human life in all civilizations. Sometimes they have mythological features and are depicted with different symbols. Some of the animals were depicted by people and given special symbols. For example, from ancient times to the present, lions are considered the king of animals, a symbol of strength and courage. The eagle, which is the emblem of the flags of Albania, Mexico, and Egypt, is a symbol of freedom and strength. Many peoples chose different animals as their symbols, and from time to time phraseological combinations related to them appeared. For example, for a lion, *avoir un coeur de lion* - to be lion-hearted, *se battre comme un lion* - to fight bravely, to fight like a lion, for an eagle, *avoir des yeux,*

un oeil d'aigle - to have a keen eye, *avoir un regard d'aigle, un coup d'oeil d'aigle* - to be eagle-eyed, to have an eagle's eye, expressions can be cited as examples.

Phraseological combinations used with zoonyms have ethnolinguistic and national characteristics, become metaphors and are distinguished by their functionality in the language. The phraseological units used with zoonyms in the Azerbaijani and French languages have derivational characteristics and are structurally homogeneous in some cases. Such phenomena can be found in languages with different structures. Zoomorphological characteristics attract attention in phraseological combinations used with animal names. Transferring human characteristics to animals (grudge, cunning, strong, coward) and using them in the form of expressions exist in both languages. Many fantastic features of animals are reflected in legends, stories and fairy tales.

Afad Gurbanov divides zoonyms into two parts; common and specific zoonyms. Common zoonyms include bird species, domestic animals, wild animals, fish species, reptiles, and insects. Special zoonyms mean names and nicknames given to animals. For example, *Kirat, Durat, Khalli* (cow), *Alabash* (dog), etc. [4, p. 97]. Phraseological combinations used with zoonyms in Azerbaijani and French languages were created on the basis of various motives. As an example, we can mention somatic, onomastic and metaphorical motifs. Examples of somatic motifs include axe-beaked, white bear, and black panther. The color of their fur is considered to be somatic motives arising from the signs of any of their organs. Animal names formed due to onomastic motives are combined with toponyms, atroponyms, ethnonyms, etc. is processed. Phrases with a zoonym component used in a metaphorical motif express expressiveness and simile.

Zoonyms and faunal expressions are rich in both languages. During the typological comparison of languages with different systems, zoonyms in French have the same meaning in the language family they belong to. Over time, these words have undergone phonetic changes, but have preserved their meaning. By comparing the process of the creation of zoonyms and their etymology, we will study the history of the zoonymic lexicon more deeply and learn the etymology of phraseological combinations formed with zoonym components. The study of phraseology, both in the mother tongue and in a foreign language, is important from the lexical, grammatical, and practical point of view. The aim is to analyze their ethnic and linguistic characteristics with a contrastive method and to investigate their equivalents in the Azerbaijani language. When comparing languages with two different systems, the unique characteristics of each language are revealed. As noted by linguists, linguistic problems arise when translating phraseological units from one language to another. This manifests itself in lexical-semantic, grammatical, syntactic structures. For example, *être comme chien et chat* is used in French; *s'entendre comme chien et chat* is the equivalent of the phrase "itlə pişik kimi yola getmək" in Azerbaijani.

In French, there are many phraseological combinations using the verbs *faire* (to do), *avoir* (to have),

être (to exist), donner (to give), mettre (to put). Negative and positive qualities of people are used in phraseological combinations through zoonyms. Avoir une faim de loup – canavar kimi ac olmaq (to be hungry like a bear). This phraseological combination expresses the same meaning in both languages however the animal changes from wolf to bear in English [5, p. 15].

Avoir la chair de poule; avoir des frissons de froid ou de peur – To shiver from the cold, to freeze, to freeze. Zoonym (poule-chicken) is used in the components of this phrase used in French, but when translated into Azerbaijani, it is more often referred to the category of somatic phraseological combinations [6, p. 15]. Ecorcher l'anguille par la queue; commencer par où l'on devrait finir – işi olduğu yerdən başlamamaq (Not to start where one's business is) nəyisə əksinə etmək (to do something opposite tərsinə), başayaq (upside down), axırdan başlamaq (start from the end).

If we literally translate this phrase in French, it means ilan balığını quyruğundan soymaq (to strip the lamprey of its tail). When we researched the French etymology of this phrase, we came across such a story. At the beginning of XVII century, skinning the lamprey from the tail was connected with a superstition. Otherwise, they believed it would bring bad luck [6]. Currently, this phrase is used in modern French and is translated into Azerbaijani as işi tərsdən başlamaq (starting a business backwards). In French, être doux comme un agneau; être gentil is translated into Azerbaijani language as quzu kimi olmaq, (being like a lamb) and has a metaphorical character.

Jeter ou se jeter dans la gueule du loup; se mettre en danger, s'exposer en danger - özünü təhlükəyə atmaq (To put oneself or someone in danger). This expression in French means özünü canavarın ağızına atmaq (to throw oneself or someone into the mouth of the wolf) [5, p. 73].

Jeter de la poudre aux yeux in French; The expression 'apparence trompeuse, chercher à faire illusion' [5, p. 73] is equivalent to the phraseological combination of 'gözə kül atmaq, gözə kül üfürmək' (throwing ash in

the eye, blowing ash in the eye) [8, p. 94] used in the Azerbaijani language.

Because they are languages with different systems, their derivational characteristics and lexical structures are different. For example, un paon – tovuzquşu (peacock), in French, this word is formed from one component, and in Azerbaijani, from two complex words. Zoonyms are also derived from zoonyms, such as aboyer-hürmək (bark), chanter-banlamaq (crow), meler- mələmək (bleat), miauler-miyovuldamaq (meow), hurler-ulamaq (howl), croisser-qarıldamaq (crawling), etc. Unlike the Azerbaijani language, the French language has a gender category. Male and female suffixes are used (un lion-une lionne)

Based on examples, when comparing phraseological combinations in Azerbaijani and French languages, they can be divided into different categories: fully equivalent ones; which are incompletely equivalent.

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